

UNRAVELLING THE MISTERIES OF ULTRAENERGETIC COSMIC RAYS WITH AUGERPRIME

BRAZIL
in the Pierre Auger
Collaboration

Participants from Brazil in the Pierre Auger Collaboration:

Ronald C. Shellard, Luis M. D. Mendes (Centro Brasileiro de Pesquisas Físicas – Rio de Janeiro – RJ)

Carla B. Bonifazi, João R. Torres de Mello Neto (Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro – Rio de Janeiro – RJ)

Bruno Lazarotto Lago (Centro Federal de Educação Tecnológica Celso Suckow da Fonseca – Campus Nova Friburgo – RJ)

Rogério Menezes de Almeida, Jaime de Oliveira, Cynthia Ventura, Diego Correa (Universidade Federal Fluminense – Rio de Janeiro – RJ)

Germano P. Guedes (Universidade Federal de Feira de Santana – Feira de Santana – Bahia)

Rita de Cássia dos Anjos (Universidade Federal do Paraná – Setor Palotina – Paraná)

Anderson C. Fauth, Carola Dobrigkeit*, José Augusto Chinellato, Márcio A. Müller, Mary Lucia Diaz Castro, Danelise Franco, Allan Payeras (Universidade Estadual de Campinas – Campinas, SP)

Marcelo A. Leigui de Oliveira (Universidade Federal do ABC – Santo André – SP)

Edivaldo Moura Santos, Ivone Albuquerque, Washington R. de Carvalho, Johnnier Perez Armand (Universidade de São Paulo – São Paulo – SP)

Carlos J. Todero Peixoto, Fernando Catalani (Universidade de São Paulo, Escola de Engenharia de Lorena, Lorena, SP)

Vitor de Souza, Humberto Martinez Huerta, Luan Arbeletche, Rodrigo Lang (Instituto de Física de São Carlos, Universidade de São Paulo – São Carlos – SP)

*** carola@ifi.unicamp.br**

Summary

1. Introduction	3
2. Research Statement	4
2.1 The Pierre Auger Observatory	4
2.2 Results of the Pierre Auger Observatory and Motivation for AugerPrime ...	8
2.3 The upgrade AugerPrime	11
2.4 Our contribution to AugerPrime	17
3. Expected results	21
4. Scientific and technological challenges, and the means and methods to meet them	24
4.1 How will we reach the goals?	27
4.2 The interpretation of the suppression in the flux	29
4.3 The proton fraction at UHE	30
4.4 Anisotropy studies with additional composition information	31
4.5 Limits of ultra-high energy photon and neutrino fluxes	32
4.6 Study of Hadronic Interactions and Fundamental Physics	32
4.7 Expected results	33
5. References	35

1. Introduction

Cosmic rays were discovered more than one hundred years ago. The existence of the ones of macroscopic energies, higher than 100 EeV, was first revealed more than fifty years ago. In spite of all the experimental efforts and the intense development of more powerful and sophisticated detectors, we still lack the knowledge about the nature and origin the ultraenergetic energetic cosmic rays.

The Pierre Auger Observatory was built twenty years ago with the goal of studying the most energetic cosmic particles. Covering 3000 km² with various types of detectors, it is the largest facility worldwide with this objective. It is taking data since January 2004 and collected data with the largest exposure reached so far by a single facility. The Observatory is located at a privileged site in Argentina and has full view of the center of our galaxy. Operated by an international collaboration of researchers from seventeen countries, its primary goal is the study of cosmic rays of the highest energies observed so far, in the region of 10¹⁷ eV and above. Brazilian physicists participate in the Pierre Auger Observatory since its very beginning in the 1990s and have been continuously contributing with an important part of the development, construction and operation of the detectors, as well as in the data analyses.

Data taken with it over the last two decades have already led to major breakthroughs in the field of ultra-high energy cosmic rays. In the last three years, the Auger Collaboration has begun an effort of a significant upgrade of its capabilities, with an emphasis on an improved mass composition determination using the surface detectors of the Observatory. Known as AugerPrime, the upgrade will include new detectors, updated and more flexible surface detector electronics, a dedicated array of buried muon detectors, and an extended duty cycle for operations of the fluorescence detectors.

The upgraded AugerPrime Observatory is foreseen to operate for the next decade. The activities in which the Brazilian scientists are involved include the installation and characterization of new detectors, the replacement and maintenance of equipment at the site, the installation and operation of a remote-control room of the fluorescence telescopes at UNICAMP, the participation in data analyses going on in various tasks inside the collaboration, shifts of data taking, and meetings.

AugerPrime is the unique cosmic-ray facility worldwide capable of assessing and answering fundamental questions about the origin of ultra-high energy cosmic rays in the next decade.

2. Research Statement

This research is nested in the broader effort of the upgrade of the Pierre Auger Observatory, dubbed **AugerPrime**. In section 2.1, we give a brief description of the Pierre Auger Observatory, and in section 2.2 we list the most important results already obtained in the last decade. We expose the scientific motivation for the upgrade of the Auger Observatory in section 2.3 and present the aims of the research in section 2.4. In the following sections, we will address the challenges we will face and the contribution we will give to the construction, maintenance, and operation of AugerPrime. Finally, we list the results we expect to obtain and the challenges we will face.

2.1 The Pierre Auger Observatory

The Pierre Auger Observatory, located near the town of Malargüe in Argentina, is the largest cosmic ray facility ever built. It is operated by an international collaboration which includes more than 400 researchers from 100 institutions of 17 countries. Brazilian physicists participate in the Pierre Auger Observatory since its very beginning in the 1990s and have been continuously contributing with an important part of the development, construction and operation of the detectors, as well as in the data analyses. Presently, twenty-nine physicists are working in the Auger Collaboration.

The main goals of the Observatory are to probe the origin and characteristics of primary cosmic rays from 10^{17} eV up to 10^{20} eV or even above. These particles are the most energetic particles observed in the Universe so far. Due to their very low flux, the study of primary cosmic rays relies on measuring at ground level the characteristics of the extensive air showers they induce in their interactions with the Earth's atmosphere. Extensive air showers initiated by cosmic particles of 10^{19} eV are composed of tens of billions of secondary particles (hadrons, muons, electrons/positrons, photons) leaving a footprint of ~ 25 km² on the ground.

The Pierre Auger Observatory is the only one of its kind situated in the Southern hemisphere. With its privileged location, the center of our Galaxy is fully in its field of view, passing only a few degrees off its zenith. Its location is centered at 35°2S, 69°2W at 1400 m above sea level, corresponding to 870 g cm⁻² of atmospheric overburden. A detailed description of the Observatory and its operation is provided in [\[1\]](#).

The Auger Observatory employs two detection techniques: a surface array of detectors (SD) spread over a huge area that continuously sample air-shower particles arriving at the ground and fluorescence telescopes (FD) that during nights without moonlight register the light emitted by nitrogen molecules in the atmosphere excited by the shower particles.

[Figure 1](#) shows an overview of the Observatory in its present configuration. It features the array of 1600 water-Cherenkov particle detectors (WCD) spread over 3000 km² overlooked by 24 air fluorescence telescopes (FD). In addition, three high elevation fluorescence telescopes (HEAT) overlook an area of 23.5 km² where additional 61 WCDs (Infilled Array) are installed.

Each WCD is filled with 12,000 liters of purified water. Cherenkov light from the passage of ultra-relativistic charged particles is collected by three 9" photomultiplier tubes (PMTs) pointing into the water. A solar power system provides power for the

PMTs and electronics package, consisting of a processor, GPS receiver, radio transceiver, and power controller. The WCD stations are placed on a triangular grid of 1500 m spacing. The SD reaches 100% detection efficiency for shower energies above 3×10^{18} eV (4×10^{18} eV) at zenith angles below 60° (above 60°). The infilled array with 23.5 km^2 consists of a denser WCD array with 750 m spacing nested within the 1500 m array. Full efficiency is reached from 3×10^{17} eV onwards for extensive air showers (EAS) with zenith angles below 55° .

Figure 1 – The layout of the Auger Observatory. Each dot corresponds to one of the 1660 surface detector stations. The four fluorescence detector sites are shown on the periphery, each with the field of view of its six telescopes (blue lines). The Coihueco site at the west hosts three extra high elevation (HEAT) telescopes (orange lines). The locations of laser (CLF, XLF) facilities are also shown in red dots. The 750-m infilled array and the AERA radio array are located a few kilometers from Coihueco.

The 24 telescopes of the FD overlook the SD array from four sites: Los Leones, Los Morados, Loma Amarilla, and Coihueco as seen in Fig.1. Each FD site houses six independent telescopes, each covering a field of view of $30^\circ \times 30^\circ$ with a minimum elevation of 1.5° above the horizon. Three additional fluorescence telescopes (HEAT) were constructed at the Coihueco site. They are very similar to the original ones but can be tilted by 29° upwards to cover the elevation range from 30° to 58° , thereby

allowing the extension of the energy spectrum and distributions of the depth of shower maximum down to the energies $\sim 10^{17}$ eV.

The SD allows for the measurement of **the lateral distribution** of the shower particles at the ground, corresponding to the signal in the detectors as a function of the respective distances to the shower core. The FD measures **the longitudinal development of air showers** along their way down to the surface. The integral of the energy deposited in fluorescence light along the path down to the ground provides an almost calorimetric estimation of the shower energy. Additionally, the atmospheric depth of the maximum of the energy deposition X_{\max} (nearly corresponding to the depth of the maximum number of particles in the shower) allows studying the composition of the primary particle that initiated the shower.

Showers measured simultaneously with both the FD and the SD are used for the calibration procedure of the energy, in which the signal at 1000 m from the shower core obtained in the SD is related to the energy of the same shower as measured by the FD. This procedure provides the energy calibration $SD \times FD$ which is then applied to all events measured with the SD, which represent the bulk of detected air showers.

High-quality devices (Balloon Launching Facility, Central Laser Facility, Extreme Laser Facility, and Lidars) are installed in the Observatory to monitor the atmospheric conditions during operation.

The Observatory includes also an array of 153 radio detection stations distributed over an area of about 17 km^2 , the Auger Engineering Radio Array (AERA), composed of antennas sensitive between 30 and 80 MHz to measure the signal of EAS in the radio band. Additionally, a dedicated detector to directly measure the muon content of EAS is currently being built. Named AMIGA (Auger Muons and Infill for the Ground Array), this enhancement consists of scintillator detectors buried in the soil at a depth of 280 g cm^{-2} next to the infilled WCD stations. Each station covers an area of 30 m^2 .

The construction of the Observatory began in 2002 after a period of prototyping and a successful operation of an engineering array. Stable data taking started in January 2004 and the baseline Observatory (without the enhancements HEAT, infilled array, AERA, and AMIGA) has been running with its full configuration since 2008. For each event, several observables can be reconstructed, the key ones being the energy of the primary particle, the arrival direction and, for the events detected by the fluorescence telescopes, the atmospheric depth of the air shower maximum, X_{\max} .

Over the last ten years, the Auger Collaboration published 91 papers (full-author-list papers). The publications in international journals with Auger Collaboration as Group Author rendered over 7,600 citations in Web of Science and 12,600 citations in INSPIRE as of November 2019. Auger collaborators (among them, many participants in the Brazilian team) gave more than 300 presentations on behalf of the Collaboration in international conferences with the publication of full papers in proceedings.

At the end of 2017, the physics magazine physicsworld.com featured two papers signed by the Auger Collaboration among The Physics World Top Ten Breakthroughs of 2017, which highlights research reported in physicsworld.com in 2017.

The Physics World 2017 Breakthrough of the Year went to the international team of astronomers and astrophysicists that ushered in a new era of astronomy by making the first-ever multimessenger observation involving gravitational waves. The Auger Collaboration took part in this effort looking for neutrinos emitted in the neutron star merger. The second Auger paper highlighted by Physics World reports the confirmation of a dipolar modulation in the flux of ultra-high energy cosmic rays by Auger, as published in *Science* on 22 September 2017, indicating that ultra-high energy cosmic rays are of extragalactic origin.

2.2 Results of the Pierre Auger Observatory and Motivation for AugerPrime

The data taken with the Pierre Auger Observatory in the last decade have led to major breakthroughs in the field of ultra-high energy cosmic rays (UHECRs). Nevertheless, looking at the various results about the energy spectrum, searches for neutral particles like photons, neutrinos and neutrons, analyses of arrival direction distributions, and studies on mass composition, it is not immediate to reach a unique and coherent picture which allows describing all the characteristics of UHECRs at once.

In this section, we briefly address the main results obtained with the Auger Observatory up to now and point out the open questions and the motivation for the upgrade.

The all-particle cosmic ray energy spectrum carries combined information about the UHECR sources and about the Galactic and/or intergalactic media through which the cosmic rays have propagated. The measured flux proves unambiguously two important features in the energy region covered by the Auger Observatory: the so-called “*ankle*” around 5×10^{18} eV, and the *flux suppression* above 4×10^{19} eV [2-4]. The statistical significance of the suppression is more than 20σ when compared to a continuous power-law extrapolation beyond the ankle feature in the spectrum.

The current limits on the photon and neutrino fluxes set by Auger exclude or strongly disfavor the possibility that the flux is produced in non-standard “top-down” processes, those in which the UHECR are supposed to be produced in decays of heavy exotic particles [5].

A dipolar large-scale anisotropy was confirmed in cosmic rays with energies above 8 EeV ($1 \text{ EeV} = 10^{18} \text{ eV}$), proving that they are indeed of extragalactic origin and opening a window on the study of the properties of extragalactic magnetic fields [6]. Strong hints of correlation of UHECR with the directions of bright, nearby starburst galaxies have been obtained in intermediate-scale anisotropy searches, while an excess of events have been seen for $E > 5.8 \times 10^{19}$ eV in the direction of the radio galaxy Centaurus A [7].

The standard astrophysical scenario dictates that the UHECRs are mainly extragalactic protons and the observed suppression of the flux is ascribed to the energy losses suffered by the particles during propagation, after having been accelerated with a power-law injection spectrum E^{-2} in sources distributed as the matter in the Universe (the so-called “*photodisintegration scenario*”). However, the energy at which the integral flux measured at Auger drops by a factor of two below what would be expected without suppression, $E_{1/2} = (23 \pm 1(\text{stat.}) \pm 4(\text{syst.})) \text{ EeV}$, is quite different from the value $E_{1/2} = 53 \text{ EeV}$ predicted for this scenario. Furthermore, this model is challenged by the results obtained by Auger on the primary composition [8–10]. Indeed, the studies of the evolution with energy of the shower development in the atmosphere point to a mass composition becoming progressively heavier with increasing energy. The heaviest component (iron) appears almost unnecessary and dispensable, while the protons add up to not more than 10% at the highest energies. Nevertheless, it must be said that the interpretation of the measured quantities which leads to this result relies very heavily on comparisons with the corresponding quantities in simulated showers. These simulations are based on extrapolations of recent data of hadronic interactions in accelerators at energies which are at least one

order of magnitude lower than the energies of the first hadronic interactions in showers detected by the Auger Observatory.

The best combined fit to the spectrum and mass composition as measured at the Pierre Auger Observatory is obtained for a model in which the sources accelerate particles to maximum energies proportional to their charge, with a harder injection spectrum E^{-1} . The observed suppression in the flux would then be ascribed to a cut-off in the energy spectra of the sources, indicating a maximum energy the source can accelerate particles ("*maximum rigidity scenario*") [11].

The interpretation of the results in terms of composition is made even more difficult by the large uncertainties in predicting hadronic multiparticle production at energies beyond those accessible in the laboratory. Different studies aiming at the evaluation of the muon content in air showers [12-14], exploiting the study of hybrid events [15], or analyzing the azimuthal asymmetry in the risetime of signals in SD [16], found inconsistencies in the modeling of hadronic interactions and muon production as implemented in the simulations. On the other hand, the Auger Observatory measured the proton-air cross section at an average $\sqrt{s} = 57$ TeV (corresponding to an average energy in the lab system $\sim 10^{18.2}$ eV) in good agreement with extrapolations from LHC energies [17a, 17b].

An upgrade of the Pierre Auger Observatory, dubbed "**AugerPrime**" [18, 19] has been planned to address the following open questions:

- Understand the origin of the flux suppression, by differentiating between a cut-off due to propagation effects and the maximum energy reached in the sources. This will allow us to provide key constraints on the sources of the ultra-high energy cosmic rays and their properties.
- Evaluate the possible existence of a fraction of protons at the highest energies. The answer to this fundamental question will set the stage for future experiments and assess the feasibility of charged particle astronomy.
- Add information about hadronic interactions in a range of energy and in a kinematic region which is not accessible in man-made accelerators. Non-standard mechanisms, such as Lorentz invariance violation or extra dimensions will also be searched for.

To reach these goals, it will be essential to provide additional measurements of composition-sensitive observables on a high statistics sample of ultra-high

energy events, thus exploiting the Surface Detector of the Pierre Auger Observatory.

The proposal to upgrade the Auger Observatory follows from a decade of discovery, and the recognition that shower-by-shower measurements of cosmic ray mass-related properties are essential to further advance the field. The proposed solution is to infer the muon component of the air showers by installing a complementary scintillator detector on top of every water-Cherenkov detector across the array, coupled with upgraded station electronics with enhanced capabilities.

AugerPrime is in the unique position worldwide of having the possibility of assessing and answering these fundamental questions in the next decade.

2.3 The upgrade AugerPrime

To extend the composition sensitivity of the Auger Observatory into the flux suppression region, the Auger Collaboration is currently initiating its upgrade named AugerPrime. A very detailed description of AugerPrime can be found in [\[18\]](#). **Below we present the various improvements planned for AugerPrime, giving more details about those in which the team will be directly involved.**

The main aim of AugerPrime is to provide, on a shower-by-shower basis, additional measurements of mass composition sensitive observables, allowing an estimation of the primary mass of highest energy cosmic rays. The study of the origin of the flux suppression will provide fundamental constraints on the astrophysical sources and will allow us to give more precise estimates of gamma-ray and neutrino fluxes at ultra-high energy. The measurement of the flux contribution of the light elements will elucidate the physics potential of existing and future cosmic-ray, neutrino, and gamma-ray detectors. The aim of AugerPrime is to reach a sensitivity as small as 10% in the flux contribution of protons in the suppression region on a shower-by-shower basis.

The determination of the primary mass composition of ultra-high energy cosmic rays is deeply related to our understanding of extensive air showers and hadronic interactions. In the Auger data, there is a disagreement between the observed and

expected muon numbers, and therefore it is of fundamental importance to study the hadronic multiparticle production in extensive air showers.

The AugerPrime upgrade consists of a series of improvements of the Pierre Auger Observatory which we describe below. **The Auger upgrade will not affect the continuous data taking and maintenance of the existing detectors. The current communication system and power system for the Surface Detector will remain unchanged. Only minor software changes are required for the central data acquisition system and for the monitoring system.**

The key elements of the upgrade consist of new plastic scintillator detectors on top of the water-Cherenkov stations (WCD) of the surface array (SD), an additional small photomultiplier (PMT) installed in each WCD for the extension of the dynamic range, and new SD electronics. Besides, an underground muon detector is going to be deployed aside each WCD in the infilled region of the Observatory, to provide direct muon measurements. The upgrade will also be complemented by extending the measurements of the existing Fluorescence Detectors (FD) into periods of higher night-sky background, to increase their duty cycle. Finally, based on the Radio Engineering Array (AERA) experience and results, a new initiative for adding a radio detector to AugerPrime is now ongoing.

The first upgrade is the installation of the new scintillator detectors above each of the existing water-Cherenkov detectors (WCD). This new detector, named as **Surface Scintillator Detector (SSD)**, consists of a plane of plastic scintillator that will be triggered by the larger WCD below it. It allows the sampling of the shower particles with *two detectors* having very different responses to muons and electromagnetic particles.

An SSD unit is a box of area $3.8 \text{ m} \times 1.3 \text{ m}$, containing two scintillator sub-modules, each composed of 24 bars of extruded scintillator of about 1.6 m length, 5 cm width and 1 cm thickness. The 3.8 m^2 scintillator planes are protected by light-tight, weatherproof enclosures, and mounted on top of the existing WCD with a strong support frame (see [Fig. 2](#)). The scintillator light will be collected with wavelength shifting fibers inserted into straight extruded holes in the scintillator planes. The fibers (Kuraray Y11(300)M S-type) are bundled and connected from both sides to one 1.5" photomultiplier tube (PMT). The PMT selected in the baseline design is the model Hamamatsu R9420. It has a bi-alkali photocathode and a quantum efficiency of about 18% at the wavelength of 500 nm. This PMT has been chosen for its excellent linear response. The design of the Surface Scintillator Detectors (SSD) is simple and

reliable, and they can be easily deployed over the full 3000 km² area of the Surface Detector array.

Figure 2 - Left: the layout of the Surface Scintillator Detector (SSD); Right: One station of the AugerPrime Engineering Array with the scintillator on top.

Another important improvement included in the AugerPrime program is the **extension of the dynamic range of the WCD**. The limited dynamic range of the SD electronics and current 9" PMTs for the very large signals at the highest energies is a drawback at present. At energies above 3×10^{19} eV more than 40% of the detected air showers suffer from saturated signals in at least the station closest to the shower core. Nonetheless, we manage to recover a large fraction of these signals based on the PMT and FADC response and the time dependence of the signal. Thus, the reconstructed observables of an air shower are not affected by having a station with a saturated signal trace. But the resolution of the reconstruction is affected. Equipping the WCD with an extra small PMT will increase the dynamic range and reduce the fraction of saturated events to less than 2%.

In more detail, the reason behind this addition lies on the saturation of the signal of the current larger PMTs for the highest-energy events in the energy region of the flux suppression. Air showers with energies above $\sim 10^{19}$ eV may saturate the current 9" PMTs in the WCD so that their energies may result underestimated. The SD data quality will be improved by extending the acquisition dynamic range in both detectors, the original WCD of the SD and the SSD, thus allowing the measurement of non-saturated signals at distances as close as 250 m from the shower core [20].

To benefit the most from the combined information of SSD and WCD, the dynamic range of both detectors should be similar. Significant signals are expected both close to the shower core and at intermediate distances, where simultaneous measurements will be most important for the separation of the different components of the shower, and furthermore, allowing a direct cross-check of the two detectors.

To increase the dynamic range, a fourth small PMT (Hamamatsu R8619, 1" diameter) is inserted in the WCD, exploiting an unused and easily accessible 30 mm window on the Tyvek bag containing the ultra-pure water. With an active area of about 1/80 with respect to the large WCD PMTs, it potentially allows for an equivalent dynamic range extension.

The required range up to about 20,000 Vertical Equivalent Muon (VEM, the reference calibration unit of the WCD high-gain channels in which the signal in the WCD is measured, defined as the signal left by a muon traversing the water in the tank vertically at its center) can be obtained by adjusting the gain in such a way that the ratio of the large to the small PMT signals be limited to a value of 32.

The linearity of the small PMT is guaranteed in the required range for a large set of voltages, down to 800 V. The power supply is provided by an external custom-made HVPS manufactured by the company CAEN for Auger.

For consistency with the associated WCD, the dynamic range in the SSD must span from the signal of a single particle, as needed for calibration, to large signals, up to $\sim 2 \times 10^4$ Minimal Ionizing Particle (MIP, the unit in which the signals in the SSD are measured). From tests, we know the number of photoelectrons per vertical minimum ionizing particle traversing the detector, giving us a scale for the measurements. Therefore, we use MIP as the physical unit for the signals in the SSD. Indeed, the SSD PMT has been chosen also based on its excellent linear response when operated at low gain, being linear within 5% for peak currents up to 160 mA (for a gain of 8×10^4). To reach the required dynamic range, the anode signal is filtered and split in two in the electronics front-end; then one of the two signals is attenuated by a factor of 4, while the other is amplified by a factor of 32.

Also, the **electronics of the SD will be modernized and improved** in the AugerPrime program. The new electronics will process the signals of the PMTs in both WCD and SSD. It will increase the data quality thanks to better timing accuracy and a faster Analog to Digital Converter sampling employing 120 MHz Flash Analog-to-Digital Converters.

Implemented in a single board, called the upgraded unified board (UUB), the electronics of the SD records the PMT signals, makes local triggering decisions, sends timestamps to the central data acquisition system and stores event data for retrieval upon a global trigger condition [21]. The upgraded electronics will allow reading the four photomultipliers of the WCD and the one in the scintillator, processing the signals at 120 MHz, corresponding to an increase of the current rate of a factor of 3 with respect to the previous rate of 40 MHz. Both the signals of the four PMTs (the three original large ones and the new small one, all in the WCD) and the one of the SSD are split and amplified to reach a gain ratio of 32 and 128 respectively. The signals are filtered and digitized following similar procedures for the WCD and SSD photomultipliers.

The new GPS receiver will allow a timing accuracy of 5 nanoseconds, about a factor two better than the current value. Faster data processing and more sophisticated local triggers are enabled using a more powerful processor and FPGA, and improved calibration and monitoring capabilities are foreseen.

The local trigger and processing capabilities are increased by using more powerful local-station processors and FPGA (field-programmable gate array), thus allowing the implementation of new triggers in addition to the current ones, e.g. combined SSD and WCD triggers. In addition, improved calibration and monitoring capabilities are foreseen.

The recorded traces can be digitally filtered and down-sampled to 40 MHz to emulate the current triggers in addition to any new ones, thus **providing backwards-compatibility with the current dataset. Furthermore, this will allow the deployment of the new electronics without stopping or disturbing the current data taking.**

The UUB is equipped with a micro-controller for the control and monitoring of the PMT high voltage, the supervision of the various supply voltages and reset functionality. More than 90 monitoring variables will be managed by the slow-control software.

Due to its dimensions, no direct calibration of the small PMT with muons is feasible. Selecting *small* shower events, the small PMT can be cross-calibrated with the large PMTs in such a way that the signal spectrum is correctly reconstructed up to about 20,000 VEM.

The SSD calibration is based on the signal of a minimum ionizing particle (MIP) going through the detector. A cross-trigger with the WCD can be used to remove all the low-

energy background. About 40% of the calibration triggers of the WCD produce a MIP in the SSD.

For both the WCD and the SSD, the cross-calibration between high gain and low gain channels is defined in the electronics, by a simple ratio between the amplified and non- amplified anode signals.

To verify and fine-tune the methods used to extract shower muon content using the SSD and WCD stations, an **underground muon detector array** dubbed AMIGA will be installed beside the WCD of the infilled area of the Observatory to provide a direct measurement of the muon content of a sample of showers observed by the upgraded Auger SD. The AMIGA detector consists of 61 units deployed on a 750-m grid, instrumenting a total area of 23.5 km². Each unit consists of a plane of plastic scintillator of about 30 m² that will be buried about 2.3 meters underground [22]. The underground muon detectors will provide important direct measurements of the muon content of the extensive air showers and its time structure, while serving as verification and fine-tuning of the methods used to extract muon information from the SSD and WCD measurements. The aim is also studying the primary cosmic-ray composition and hadronic interactions in a region of energy corresponding to the transition from galactic to extragalactic cosmic rays.

Although not explicitly part of AugerPrime, it is worth mentioning that also **resistive plate chambers** (RPC) will be deployed below 40 WCDs to permit to further cross-check the muon content of a sample of showers. Part of these RPCs was already assembled at the Instituto de Física da USP de São Carlos, in collaboration with scientists from institutions in Portugal. A description of these RPCs is given in [23]. Twenty-two RPCs are already being installed at the Auger Observatory, while more are currently being assembled at CBPF, also in close collaboration with the Portuguese colleagues.

An engineering array of radio detectors (AERA) has been running in the Pierre Auger Observatory for a few years. With the collected data, it was possible to demonstrate the feasibility of radio detection with a grid of antennas at 1500 m mutual distances and measure horizontal showers (zenith angles between 60° and 84°) which cover an area of several km² on the ground [24]. Based on these results, a full **radio upgrade** of the Pierre Auger Observatory has been proposed where each WCD of the SD will be equipped with a radio antenna mounted on its top surface [25].

The new radio detectors will operate together with the upgraded SD, forming a unique setup to measure the properties of cosmic rays above 10^{17.5} eV. For horizontal

showers, they will nicely complement the information on the particle type we will get from the WCD+SSD, thereby increasing the exposure for mass-sensitive investigations [25].

Finally, in parallel with the Surface Detector upgrade, the operation mode of the Fluorescence Detector (FD) will be changed to **extend FD measurements** into periods with higher night sky background [26]. The Auger Fluorescence Detector (FD) provides information about extensive air showers such as a model-independent energy reconstruction and longitudinal development profiles of the extensive air showers. We assess the mass composition through the longitudinal development of showers measured with the FD. It is noteworthy that at the highest energies above the flux suppression at 5×10^{19} eV, FD data are sparse. This is a consequence of the main limitation of the FD, which is its duty cycle, currently at the level of 15%: the flux is suppressed, UHECRs are rare, and the short duty cycle does not favor the detection of a large number of events with the FD. The FD duty cycle is currently limited to about 15%, the operations being restricted to dark and moonless nights. The current criteria for FD measurements require the Sun to be more than 18° below the horizon, the Moon to be below the horizon for more than three hours, and the illuminated fraction of the Moon to be below 70%. A significant increase of about 50% in the current duty cycle can be obtained by extending the FD operations to times with larger night sky background, relaxing the second and third requirements above. During such operating conditions, the PMT gains must be reduced by lowering the supplied high voltage to avoid high anode current and, therefore, a deterioration of the PMTs. The HV power supplies used for the FD allow switching between two high-voltage levels, and the PMTs can be operated at the nominal gain (standard operation mode) and a lower gain (new operation mode for periods of high night sky background). By reducing the supplied high voltage, the PMT gains can be reduced by a factor of 10.

2.4 Our contribution to AugerPrime

We will contribute to the effort of AugerPrime on various fronts.

2.4.1

First, we will be responsible for the addition of part of the small PMTs to be installed in each WCD for the extension of its dynamic range. The team will share this

responsibility working in close collaboration with the group of the Osservatorio Astrofisico di Torino (INAF) and INFN, Sezione di Torino, in Turin, Italy, in the effort to overcome the saturation of the large PMTs of the surface stations by adding a fourth small PMT in each station. This effort involves the acquisition of the PMTs, HV, cables and further components, characterizing them and assembling them inside the WCD at the Auger site in Argentina.

The addition of a fourth, small-area PMT (SPMT) in each WCD will drastically reduce the number of events with saturated signals. In addition, the data acquisition system of the new surface detectors will provide improved time and charge resolution of the digitized PMT outputs by using 120 MHz, 12-bit fast ADCs for a better reconstruction of the shape of the signals.

The WCDs in the field have a redundant set of three identical, large collecting area (230mm diameter) Photonis XP1805 photomultipliers. We refer to these as the Large PMTs (LPMT), **which will be kept in operation without upgrade**. In addition, the fourth, new phototube with a significantly smaller cathode surface, called the small PMT (SPMT), will be added to each WCD to extend its dynamic range.

The Auger Collaboration has tested and qualified three models with the required performance for the SPMT (Hamamatsu R8619, Hamamatsu R6094, ETL9107B). The tests were driven by simple technical and system considerations: its diameter, photocathode active area; linearity, time response, procurement and cost. The R8619 from Hamamatsu is the chosen baseline SPMT model, as it satisfies all technical requirements and is industrially produced in large quantities, with benefits on yield and cost. Prototype mechanics for supporting the SPMT in the LED window were successfully built with 3D printers and are being tested in the field. Molds will be engineered for cost-effective mass fabrication.

The operating LPMTs are equipped with an active base which includes the High Voltage (HV) resistive divider, a HV DC-DC converter module and a charge amplifier for the dynode readout. The base is soldered to the PMT leads and protected with insulating silicone potting. Given the high level of moisture and severe temperature cycles inside the WCD, the potting proved to be far from ideal, resulting in a low but visible number of failures in the field, which will be minimized in the upgrade with an improved design for the SPMT, with the goal to reducing the necessary maintenance operations to a negligible level.

Therefore, a simpler, passive resistive base for the new SPMT was designed, and the HV DC-DC converter moved to a separate module that can be conveniently located

outside the WCD, and away from the moisture. The base will be located inside the WCD and will not be potted, but simply coated. The HV module will be housed in a dedicated box next to the station electronics.

A new model for the HV DC-DC converter (CAEN-A7501P) was qualified, with slightly better thermal stability, operational temperature range and power consumption with respect to the module used for the LPMTs (SensTech-PS2010/12).

The Upgraded Unified Board (UUB) will implement a new version of the Slow Control able to handle up to six HV lines, and will be used to drive the large PMTs, the new small PMT and up to two additional PMTs for the Scintillator Detector. Separate HV boxes for the small PMT and the Scintillator Detector will connect to the Slow Control on the one hand and to the PMTs on the other.

2.4.2

Secondly, we will resume the responsibility for the maintenance of the surface detectors, mainly for their power supply. The team already carried out this responsibility from 2010 until 2016. With the installation of the scintillator detectors on top of each WCD and the new electronics, the reliance on the power supply is crucial for all detectors operating properly and 100% of the time. The power supply has been a strong boundary condition during the whole planning of the upgrade in order not to surpass the nominal capability of 24 V. As for the maintenance, we will take the responsibility to maintain the power supply of all the 1660 SSDs of AugerPrime, changing components whenever needed. We foresee that in the period of five years all the 1660 detectors will acquire new power supplies. The members of the team will participate regularly in maintenance shifts of the SSD, which are done remotely from the respective home institutions.

2.4.3

Thirdly, the team will participate in shifts of data taking with the fluorescence telescopes. As already mentioned, the periods of data taking with the telescopes in AugerPrime will be extended to include nights with higher light background. Therefore, the shifts will span a longer period and require more shifters. The possibility of shifters participating from their home institutions will be open, and we intend to take advantage of it by assembling a room at UNICAMP with the necessary equipment. This room will be used for remote shifts by members of the team from other institutions from São Paulo. Not all FD shifts can be done remotely, and it is important that some

shifts are done from the site in Malargüe. The shifter must have participated at least once in person in a shift to be able to do the same shift remotely from Campinas.

2.4.4

We also intend to continue to deploy, test and operate at the Auger site the resistive plate chambers (RPC) we assembled in Brazil. in collaboration with scientists from institutions in Portugal. Half of these RPCs are presently being installed below WCDs at the site and will allow an independent measurement of the muon content of the showers crossing the detector and thus, a cross-check of the SSD+WCD measurements in what concern the muonic component.

2.4.5

Finally, we will keep our strong participation in the various analyses performed on data from AugerPrime. Members of our team lead important tasks and analyses: until recently, Edivaldo Moura Santos was the convener of the Arrival Direction/Anisotropy Studies task over three years, and Vitor de Souza is one of the leaders of the Mass Composition task and a member of the Working Group for joint analyses about this topic by the Telescope Array and Auger Collaborations. Members of the team are continuously involved in Editorial Boards of papers under preparation for submission to journals and have given talks (some of them invited) in the name of the Collaboration in important international conferences over the last ten years, presenting important results of analyses to the community. Members of our team will participate and even lead some of the tasks inside the collaboration. The tasks in which we will be directly involved are those of Mass Composition, Hadronic Interactions, Arrival Directions, and Photons.

2.4.6

An important aim of this research will be the education of students at all levels. Cosmic rays are a fascinating topic in astrophysics and most attractive for young students, providing them with the possibility of acquiring state-of-the-art knowledge as well as international insertion of their work. Therefore, we will enroll in all activities graduate and undergraduate students as well as postdocs. Graduate students will develop their MSc and PhD theses.

To promote training of qualified human resources, we plan to organize biannual Schools on ultra-high energy cosmic rays for graduate and undergraduate students with the aim of attracting good students for doing their PhD.

3. Expected results.

The upgrade AugerPrime is foreseen to operate at least until the end of 2025, with the possibility of an extension. This period will triple the statistics of the data set with respect to the one at the end of 2012. However, increasing the statistics of the measured showers will not be enough to answer the key questions outlined in the previous sections. Therefore, we aim that the upgrade of the Pierre Auger Observatory ensures that the collected data provide additional information to allow one to answer the open questions by:

1. Elucidating the mass composition and the origin of the flux suppression at the highest energies, i.e. the differentiation between the energy-loss effects due to propagation and the maximum energy of particles injected by astrophysical sources.

2. Searching for a flux contribution of protons up to the highest energies, aiming to reach a sensitivity to a contribution as small as 10% in the flux suppression region. Moreover, the flux of secondary gamma-rays and neutrinos due to proton energy loss processes will be predicted.

3. Studying extensive air showers and hadronic multiparticle production. This will include the exploration of fundamental particle physics at energies beyond those accessible at man-made accelerators, and the derivation of constraints on new physics phenomena, such as Lorentz invariance violation or extra dimensions.

We expect that these goals will be attained by providing event-by-event composition-sensitive measurements by increasing the ability to recognize and separate the different components of air showers.

Since October 2016, an Engineering Array of twelve AugerPrime stations is taking data in the field in Argentina, with the aim of testing and monitoring the performances of the upgraded detectors. The results are promising and certify that all components are working as expected.

The logarithm of the charge spectrum in one of the upgraded AugerPrime WCD stations is shown in [Fig. 3 \(left\) \[27\]](#). The dynamic range is extended to more than 20,000 VEM by means of the small PMT, as one can see by comparing the unsaturated spectrum measured by the large PMTs (magenta histogram) to the one obtained with the small PMT (brown curve). The reconstruction resolution obtained

with the small PMT is better than 5% above 3000 VEM, which corresponds to the signal produced at 250 m from the core in showers of 10 EeV.

The very good linearity in the behavior of the photomultipliers of the SSD guarantees the possibility of measuring signals up to about 20,000 MIP. As shown in Fig. 3 (right), for one SSD-PMT the non-linearity stays below 5% up to the highest densities.

Figure 3. Left: Charge spectrum in one of the upgraded WCD stations, as measured by the large PMTs (pink: unsaturated, green: saturated) and by the small PMT (brown: unsaturated, blue: saturated). Right: Linearity behavior of one of the SSD-PMT [27].

The correlation between the signals in one of the WCD and in the corresponding scintillator is shown in Fig.4 (left), where both scales are expressed in the corresponding physical units (VEM for the WCD PMTs and MIP for the SSD PMT). The signals in the WCD are measured up to saturation (~ 650 VEM) by the large PMTs (black dots). In the superposition region and above the large PMT saturation, they are derived from the small PMT (red dots). The obtained correlation demonstrates the validity of the independent calibration procedures and shows that the required dynamic range in the upgraded Surface Detector is nicely covered up to the highest particle densities.

The reconstructed lateral distribution function for one of the events collected in the region of the Engineering Array is shown in Fig. 4 (right). The signal recorded in the upgraded WCD (red dots) is in very good agreement with expectations, following the lateral distribution reconstructed by means of the standard stations. The SSD signal, in blue, results to be relatively lower than the WCD ones, as expected due to the different sensitivity of the two detectors to the electromagnetic component of the

showers at different core distances and to the relatively smaller area of the SSD with respect to the WCD.

Figure 4. Left: Correlation of signals in SSD vs WCD. The large PMTs are used up to the saturation (black dots); the measurements are extended further by means of the small PMT (red dots). Right: Lateral distribution of an event close to the Engineering Array [27].

To demonstrate that the addition of the small PMT solves the problem of the saturation of the signal in the large PMT, Fig. 5 below shows the lateral distribution function of one of the measured events, reconstructed with $E = 1.59 \times 10^{19}$ eV and arrival direction $\theta = 16^\circ$, reconstructed using the signal of the small PMT in substitution to the signal of the saturated large PMT. For the station closest to the shower core (here at 153 m) both the saturated signal from the LPMTs and the full signal from the SPMT are shown.

Figure 5- Lateral distribution for one event measured in the engineering array of AugerPrime. The signal in the station closest to the shower core (153 m) is recorded by the SPMT (red point); the signal in the LPMTs is saturated (red triangle) [18].

4. Scientific and technological challenges, and the means and methods to meet them

At the time when the construction of the Pierre Auger Observatory started twenty years ago, the main goal boosting the research was to verify the existence or not of a suppression in the cosmic ray flux at the energies predicted by Greisen, Zatsepin and Kuzmin soon after the discovery of the delta resonance still in the 1960s. As a result of the data gathered since then, the Auger Collaboration has not only certified the flux suppression with an accuracy of 20σ but established other properties of cosmic rays of extreme energies.

The discoveries made over the past decade have transformed our understanding of UHECRs and their sources. Before the development of very large hybrid detectors as the Auger Observatory, it was commonly believed that ultrahigh-energy cosmic rays were protons. The protons with energies above the threshold to create a delta were supposed to interact with the photons of the cosmic microwave background, losing energy and causing the predicted flux suppression. Furthermore, the transition from Galactic to extragalactic cosmic rays was supposed to occur at a few EeV and mark a shift from Galactic iron to extragalactic protons.

But the Auger data revealed a far more complex scenario. The Auger energy spectrum can be roughly described by a twice-broken power law. The first break is a hardening of the spectrum, known as “the ankle.” The second, an abrupt softening of the spectrum, which could be interpreted as the predicted cutoff mentioned above. Measurements of mass composition of cosmic rays at the highest energies revealed a light composition (mainly H-He) at energies up to a few EeV and becoming gradually heavier (as C-N or even Fe) as the energy increases. Thus, the most recent data reveal a more complex evolution of the cosmic-ray composition with energy that challenges the old simplistic models.

Analyses of the arrival directions of cosmic rays with energies near that where the “ankle” in the spectrum is seen, are highly isotropic, arguing that these protons must be of extragalactic origin. At higher energies, Galactic and extragalactic deflections of UHECR nuclei are expected to smear point sources into warm/hot spots, for which

evidence is accumulating. Auger has reported a possible correlation with nearby starburst galaxies or events above 39 EeV and a slightly weaker association with active galactic nuclei emitting gamma-rays is above 60 EeV. A dipole in the arrival-direction distribution with a significance of 5σ was also reported recently by the Auger Collaboration, pointing at 125° from the center of our Galaxy thus indicating an extragalactic origin of cosmic rays at the highest energies.

A neutrino flux is also expected from the decays of pions produced by ultra-energetic protons interacting on their route to Earth. Auger has searched for such neutrinos without any candidate being observed so far. The non-observation of high-energy showers initiated by neutrinos beyond background expectations severely constrains the magnitude of the very high-energy neutrino flux. The limits on the flux set by Auger already challenge models in which the highest-energy cosmic rays are protons.

It must be added that to the knowledge of the accurate composition it is essential to understand the physics in extensive air showers correctly. This understanding requires accurate modeling of particle physics at center-of-mass energies up to hundreds of TeV – far beyond the 14 TeV in reach of the LHC. Analyses of the muon component in air showers done by the Auger Collaboration have revealed stress between observations and model predictions which required a better understanding and modelling of the hadronic interactions occurring at the highest energies.

Finally, Auger data have shown its importance also at multimessenger analyses, as revealed in the recent observation of the binary neutron star merger reported in 2017, where Auger checked for neutrinos in correlation with the gravitational waves detected by LIGO and Virgo. The knowledge accumulated by the Pierre Auger Observatory about ultra-high energy cosmic rays led to major advances in our understanding of their properties. Nevertheless, the many unknowns about the nature and distribution of the sources, the primary composition and the underlying hadronic interactions prevent the emergence of a uniquely consistent picture. Despite the advances of our understanding of UHECRs, many questions remain open. The Pierre Auger Collaboration has the potential of answering the open questions enumerated above and motivated the effort of upgrading the Observatory to address the following questions:

- **Origin of the flux suppression:** Is the flux suppression caused by energy losses of cosmic rays during the propagation from their sources to Earth or by the maximum energy of the astrophysical accelerators? Or is it caused by a combination of both?

- **Prospects for particle astronomy:** What is the fraction of light elements at ultra-high energies? Is this fraction large enough to perform charged-particle astronomy with tolerable distortions from Galactic and extragalactic magnetic fields? How do the observed anisotropies depend on the particle rigidity?
- **Fundamental physics at ultra-high energies:** Are the inconsistencies between air shower simulations and the surface detector data due to fundamental shortcomings in our understanding of hadronic multiparticle production? Can we constrain new physics phenomena, such as Lorentz invariance violation or extra dimensions at energies beyond those accessible at human-made accelerators?

In AugerPrime, the team will guarantee the results listed below:

- The continuous operation of the power supply of the WCDs and SSDs allows AugerPrime to take data taking during 100% of the time.
- The additional small PMTs that the team will characterize and install in the WCDs will assure an increase in the accuracy of the energy estimation of air showers with energies above 10^{19} eV, which are crucial for answering the three questions above.
- The lateral distribution functions of these showers used for the energy estimate will be reconstructed down to ~ 200 m from the core, as already shown in [Fig. 5](#).
- The cross-check of measurements of muons with the RPCs will assure better calibration between the WCDs and SSDs.
- The extension of the period of FD shifts in which we take part will assure collecting more high-energy air showers above 10^{19} eV, assuring a better knowledge of the longitudinal development of air showers and consequently, of X_{\max} , and a better energy calibration.
- Improving the accuracy of energy, depth of shower maximum, and muon number will allow answering the questions above, as will be explained below.

The main focus of the upgrade AugerPrime is to provide a high statistics sample of events with mass information at ultra-high energies which will be achieved by increasing the amount of information extracted from air shower with the surface detector that operates 100% of the time.

Answering the questions above represents the major scientific challenge for AugerPrime. The upgraded detectors will allow us to collect data with higher

quality, facing the challenge of installing new components and detectors in the field in addition to the existing ones and extracting high-quality data.

The construction and completion of AugerPrime represents a new challenge for the Auger Collaboration. The success of the enterprise depends on technical coordination, integration, procurement, quality of components and operation. The different parts of the upgrade have been distributed between various institutions, sometimes even for one single component there are institutions in two or more countries responsible for it. This implies in standardization and integration of the research. This is a challenge for the team in so far that also on the timely completion of the multiple tasks under our responsibility will depend the success of AugerPrime.

The team of researchers will be working in close collaboration with the group of the Osservatorio Astrofisico di Torino (INAF) and INFN, Sezione di Torino, in Turin, Italy, in the effort to overcome the saturation of the surface stations adding small PMTs. This implies in characterizing and calibrating these PMTs following a standard procedure, and then installing them in the SD stations on the site. The work will be distributed among the participating institutions in the research.

The team will also continue to collaborate with the colleagues from other institutions in Brazil and Portugal, testing the resistive plate chambers built in Brazil. Simultaneous measurements of the muon content in air showers with the various detectors will provide a further cross-check of the results.

4.1 How will we reach the goals?

One of the key aims and **scientific challenges** of AugerPrime is to discriminate between different mass compositions and physics scenarios in the energy range of the flux suppression. The most direct technique to evaluate the muon component exploits the different responses of the WCD and SSD at station level, relating the total signals in two detectors, S_{WCD} and S_{SSD} , to the electromagnetic and muonic fluxes at the ground.

Solving the puzzle implies in being able to disentangle the signals of the electromagnetic and muonic components from the signals registered in the WCD and SSD at a shower-by-shower basis. For the combination of the SSD and the Auger WCD, it is possible to relate the signal expressed in its physical units MIP measured

with the SSD, S_{SSD} , and the signal in its physical units VEM measured by the WCD, S_{WCD} , to the electromagnetic energy flux F_{em} and the muonic flux F_{μ} at the ground by a matrix equation (after correcting for the different areas of the detectors).

Employing a matrix inversion method [28], the muonic signal in the WCD can be derived as $S_{\mu,WCD} = a S_{WCD} + b S_{SSD}$, where the coefficients a and b , although derived from simulations, show only a very weak dependence on the mass and arrival direction of the primary particles and on the hadronic interaction models used in the Monte Carlo.

The muon signals so obtained are subject to large fluctuations, being restricted to individual stations. The performances of the method can be improved when the reconstructed signals at station level are used to evaluate the lateral distribution function of the air shower. The matrix inversion method can then be applied to evaluate the muon signal at 800 m from the core, $S_{\mu}(800)$. Applying the matrix inversion method on simulated showers and using $S_{\mu}(800)$ as estimator of the composition, showed that it is possible to separate proton and iron primaries at small zenith angles for energies larger than $10^{19.5}$ eV.

In Fig.6 (left), the reconstruction bias (solid symbols) and the resolution (open symbols) of the muonic signal contribution for individual detector stations are shown for two different primary compositions: at 1000 m from the core, a resolution of 20 to 30% can be achieved.

An alternative and more general approach based on the properties of universality¹ of air showers [29] or else multivariate analyses will also permit to take advantage of all the information provided by AugerPrime, not only by correlating the detector signals at different distances to the core but also considering their temporal structure (arrival times of the particles at the stations). In this case, an event-by-event reconstruction permits to derive not only the energy, but also the depth of maximum shower development in atmosphere (X_{max}) and the number of muons (N_{μ}) using the information from the scintillators combined with the WCD data. The bias and

¹ “Shower universality” refers to the fact that the average properties of the cascade can, to a large extent, be described in terms only of their energy and shower “age”, the stage of its development. To first approximation, there is no direct dependence on the primary mass nor zenith angle. This is a very remarkable result. Despite the vast number of interactions in an air shower, its overall shape as well as the time profiles of particles reaching ground can be described very well with very few measurable quantities. In the literature it has been described for the electromagnetic component of showers. The concept can also be extended to hadronic showers by introducing one additional parameter, the muon scale N_{μ} . The result is a model that describes showers initiated by protons, nuclei up to iron as well as photon showers using only three parameters: E , X_{max} and N_{μ} .

resolution in the evaluation of N_μ are shown in Fig.6 (right), as function of composition and energy. The reconstruction bias for X_{\max} is less than 15 g/cm^2 with a resolution improving from 40 g/cm^2 at 10^{19} eV to 25 g/cm^2 at 10^{20} eV .

Figure 6. Left: Reconstruction bias (full symbols) and resolution (empty ones) for the muonic signal derived with the matrix inversion method in individual stations, as a function of distance to the shower core, for protons (circles) and iron nuclei (squares). Right: Relative difference between the number of muons reconstructed in individual showers using shower universality and the true (Monte Carlo) ones as a function of energy for different primary species. Error bars represent the RMS of the distributions [18].

4.2 The interpretation of the suppression in the flux

To explore the power of AugerPrime with respect to meeting the scientific goals, the Auger Collaboration simulated two sets of mock data corresponding to seven years of data taking with AugerPrime and to an exposure of $50,000 \text{ km}^2 \text{ sr yr}$, assuming the two different simplified models mentioned previously: a maximum-rigidity scenario ("Scenario 1") and a photodisintegration one ("Scenario 2"). While the two scenarios approximately reproduce the spectrum and the X_{\max} and its fluctuations $\sigma(X_{\max})$ so far measured by the Pierre Auger Observatory, they are generated by very different compositions and spectra at the sources.

These two benchmark models approximately reproduce the energy spectrum and X_{\max} distributions as measured in Auger above $10^{18.7} \text{ eV}$, as resulting from a numerical fit following the method described in [11].

The distributions of the mean X_{\max} and its fluctuations and the mean muon number as predicted based on the two scenarios are shown in Figs. 7 as a function of energy for two extreme nuclear masses, proton and iron. The values of the fluctuations $\text{RMS}(X_{\max})$ include both the shower-to-shower fluctuations and the detector

resolution. The total muon number is shown relative to that expected from a mix of equal fractions of primaries. Although the expected values are quite similar below $10^{19.2}$ eV, a range already covered by the FD, the models predict quite different results in the highest energy region, showing that the two scenarios can be distinguished with high statistics and significance in seven years of measurements.

Figure 7 - Predicted mean depth of shower maximum X_{max} , its fluctuations $\sigma(X_{max})$ and the relative muon number at 38° evaluated for the two benchmark scenarios [18, 27]. Scenario 1: maximum rigidity model; Scenario 2: photodisintegration model, using simulated SD data only, for pure proton and pure iron compositions.

4.3 The proton fraction at UHE

In the scenario of a **maximum rigidity model**, no protons can reach us from above 5×10^{19} eV, while on the contrary, a large fraction of them would be seen in the **photodisintegration** scenario. To explore the feasibility of detection of a tiny fraction of protons with AugerPrime in the framework of Scenario 1, the Auger Collaboration also simulated showers adding artificially a contribution of 10% protons to Scenario 1. The results of these simulations demonstrated that the best separation power can be achieved by constructing a combined significance using all observables at our disposal: the mean depth of shower maximum X_{max} , its fluctuations, the mean relative muon number at 38° , $R_{\mu,38}$ (using the median angle to get rid of the dependencies of the total muon number on energy and zenith angle) and its fluctuations. Using this combination and integrating above 10^{19} eV, the results shown in Fig. 8 indicate the possibility of observing a fraction of protons as low as 10% at the highest energies with more than 5σ after five years of operation of AugerPrime [27].

Figure 8. The significance of each measured quantity in distinguishing scenarios of maximum rigidity with and without at least 10% protons respectively) as a function of the operation time of AugerPrime [27].

4.4 Anisotropy studies with additional composition information

To study the gain in sensitivity with AugerPrime in the search for the sources of ultra-high energy cosmic rays, the Auger Collaboration used the arrival directions of 454 events with $E > 4 \times 10^{19}$ eV measured at zenith angle $< 60^\circ$, [30], assigning to them random X_{\max} values according to scenario 1. A 10%-enhanced proton fraction was then implemented as in the previous study. Furthermore, we randomly assigned to 50% of these protons an arrival direction corresponding within 3° to one of the AGNs of the Swift-BAT catalog, chosen among those with distances within 100 Mpc [31].

The angular correlation obtained from this study resulted not significant when considering the complete data set of 454 events without composition information, but with the proton-enriched sample a correlation in excess of 3σ is clearly evident. As expected, no excess of pairs is found with the AGNs for the proton deprived selection, as in this case the angular correlation is just due to statistical fluctuations [27].

4.5 Limits of ultra-high energy photon and neutrino fluxes

Auger observations provided the currently most stringent limits on the flux of photons at energies above 10^{19} eV and severe constraints on cosmogenic neutrinos [32, 33].

Even better limits can be obtained with AugerPrime: five more years of data will provide a large increase in statistics, the new electronics will allow to introduce new and more efficient triggers, a reduction of the hadronic background will be possible thanks to an improved muon discrimination.

In Fig. 9, the current limits for both photons and neutrinos are shown together with preliminary calculations of the expected sensitivities from AugerPrime (dashed lines).

This ideal case assumes complete rejection of the hadronic background. In the photon case, the introduction of the new triggers permits to extend the measurement with SD below 10^{19} eV.

Figure 9. Expected sensitivity on the flux of photons (left) and neutrinos (right) [32,33]. For photons, full black lines show more conservative estimates based only on the increase of statistics.

4.6 Study of Hadronic Interactions and Fundamental Physics

AugerPrime can shed light on whether the inconsistencies between air shower simulations and experimental data are due to fundamental shortcomings in our understanding of hadronic multiparticle production. Since the electromagnetic energy

deposit in the atmosphere is mainly due to the first high-energy interactions, while on the other hand muons at ground come as products of low energy interactions, an event-by-event correlation between the depth of shower maximum X_{\max} and the muon content R_{μ} in showers generated by ultra-high energy cosmic rays can bring strong constraints on hadronic interaction models [34].

A high-resolution measurement of the muon number such as the one expected from AugerPrime is a very powerful observable also to look for exotic interaction scenarios. As an example, if Lorentz invariance violation effects exist, the absorption and energy losses of

UHECRs during propagation would be modified. Furthermore, strong changes in the development of shower produced by the interaction of UHECRs with nuclei in the atmosphere may also be visible [35].

4.7 Expected results

With AugerPrime we expect to exploit the improved quality of the data gathered with the upgraded detectors and its capacity in distinguishing the mass composition to answer fundamental questions about the primary cosmic rays of extreme energies.

The results expected in AugerPrime are to:

- i) elucidate the mass composition and the origin of the flux suppression, thus setting key constraints on the sources of ultra-high energy cosmic rays and their properties. Knowing the mass composition, we will be able to differentiate between the scenario of energy-loss effects during the propagation of the particles up to Earth and the possibility that the astrophysical sources have reached their maximum capacity of injecting energetic particles.
- ii) evaluate the possible existence of a fraction of primary protons at the highest energies thus permitting analyses of arrival directions for these primary particles; with a fraction of protons of at least of 10%, doing cosmic-ray astronomy will be in reach.
- iii) study the properties of hadronic multiparticle production in extensive air showers in a range of energy and a kinematic region which are not accessible at human-made accelerators. These studies will include the exploration of fundamental

particle physics at the highest energies and the derivation of constraints on new physics phenomena.

AugerPrime is in the unique position worldwide of having the possibility of assessing and answering these fundamental questions in the next decade.

5. References

- [1] A. Aab et al., The Pierre Auger Collaboration, “The Pierre Auger Cosmic Ray Observatory”, Nucl. Instrum. Meth. A 798 (2015) 172-213, [arXiv: 1502.01323\[astro-ph.HE\]](#).
- [2] J. Abraham et al., The Pierre Auger Collaboration, “Observation of the suppression of the flux of cosmic rays above 4×10^{19} eV,” Phys. Rev. Lett. 101 (2008) 061101, [arXiv:0806.4302](#) [astro-ph].
- [3] J. Abraham et al., The Pierre Auger Collaboration, “Measurement of the energy spectrum of cosmic rays above 10^{18} eV using the Pierre Auger Observatory,” Phys. Lett. B 685 (2010) 239–246, [arXiv: 1002.1975](#) [astro-ph.HE].
- [4] A. Aab et al., The Pierre Auger Collaboration, “Measurement of the cosmic ray spectrum above 4×10^{18} eV using inclined events detected with the Pierre Auger Observatory,” JCAP 08 (2015) 049, [arXiv: 1503.07786](#) [astro-ph.HE].
- [5] M. Unger for the Pierre Auger Collaboration, “Highlights from the Pierre Auger Observatory”, Highlight talk in Proc. 35th Int. Cosmic Ray Conf., Busan (Korea), PoS(ICRC2017) 1102 (2017), also in [arXiv: 1710.09478](#).
- [6] A. Aab et al. (Pierre Auger Collaboration), “Observation of a Large-scale Anisotropy in the Arrival Directions of Cosmic Rays above 8×10^{18} eV” , Science 357, 1266 (2017), also in [arXiv: 1709.07321](#).
- [7] A. Aab et al. (Pierre Auger Collaboration), “An Indication of Anisotropy in Arrival Directions of Ultra-high-energy Cosmic Rays through Comparison to the Flux Pattern of Extragalactic Gamma-Ray Sources”, Astrophys. J. 853, L29 (2018), [arXiv: 1801.06160](#).
- [8] A. Aab et al. (Pierre Auger Collaboration), “Depths of Maximum of Air-Shower Profiles at the Pierre Auger Observatory: Composition Implications”, Phys. Rev.D90, 122006 (2014), [arXiv: 1409.5083](#).
- [9] A. Aab et al. (Pierre Auger Collaboration), “Evidence for a mixed mass composition at the ‘ankle’ in the cosmic-ray spectrum”, Phys. Lett.B762, 288 (2016), [arXiv: 1609.08567](#).
- [10] A. Aab et al. (Pierre Auger Collaboration), “Inferences on Mass Composition and Tests of Hadronic Interactions from 0.3 to 100 EeV using the water-Cherenkov Detectors of the Pierre Auger Observatory”, Phys. Rev.D96, 122003 (2017), [arXiv: 1710.07249](#).
- [11] A. Aab et al. (Pierre Auger Collaboration), “Combined fit of spectrum and composition data as measured by the Pierre Auger Observatory”, JCAP04, 038 (2017), [arXiv: 1612.07155](#).
- [12] A. Aab et al. (Pierre Auger Collaboration), “Muons in air showers at the Pierre Auger Observatory: mean number in highly inclined events”, Phys. Rev.D91, 032003 (2015), ERRATA: Phys. Rev. D 91, 059901 (2015), [arXiv: 1408.1421](#) [astro-ph.HE].
- [13] A. Aab et al. (Pierre Auger Collaboration), Phys. Rev. D90, 012012 (2014). Erratum-ibid: 92 (2015) 019903, [arXiv: 1408.1421](#) [astro-ph.HE].

- [14] M. Mallamaci for the Pierre Auger Collaboration, Proc. 35th Int. Cosmic Ray Conf., Busan (Korea), PoS(ICRC2017) 509 (2017), also in [arXiv:1708.06592](#).
- [15] A. Aab et al. (Pierre Auger Collaboration), "Testing hadronic interactions at ultrahigh energies with air showers measured by the Pierre Auger Observatory", Phys. Rev. Lett. 117, 192001 (2016), [arXiv: 1610.08509](#).
- [16] A. Aab et al. (Pierre Auger Collaboration), "Azimuthal asymmetry in the risetime of the Surface Detector signals of the Pierre Auger Observatory", Phys. Rev. D93, 072006 (2016), [arXiv: 1604.00978](#).
- [17a,17b] P. Abreu et al., The Pierre Auger Collaboration, "Measurement of the proton-air cross-section at $\sqrt{s} = 57$ TeV with the Pierre Auger Observatory", Phys. Rev. Lett. 109 (2012) 62002, [arXiv:1208.1520](#); Ralf Ulrich for the Pierre Auger Collaboration, "Extension of the measurement of the proton-air cross section with the Pierre Auger Observatory", Proc. of 34th Int. Cosmic Ray Conf., The Hague, The Netherlands, ICRC 2015 [arXiv:1509.03732](#).
- [18] The Pierre Auger Collaboration, "The Pierre Auger Observatory Upgrade: AugerPrime. Preliminary Design Report", (2016), in [arXiv:1604.03637](#).
- [19] D. Martello for the Pierre Auger Collaboration, Proc. 35th Int. Cosmic Ray Conf., Busan (Korea), PoS(ICRC2017) 383 (2017), also in [arXiv:1708.06592](#).
- [20] A. Castellina for the Pierre Auger Collaboration, Proc. 35th Int. Cosmic Ray Conf., Busan (Korea), PoS(ICRC2017) 397 (2017), also in [arXiv:1708.06592](#).
- [21] T. Suomijarvi for the Pierre Auger Collaboration, Proc. 35th Int. Cosmic Ray Conf., Busan (Korea), PoS(ICRC2017) 450 (2017), also in [arXiv:1708.06592](#).
- [22] M.J. Figueira for the Pierre Auger Collaboration, Proc. 35th Int. Cosmic Ray Conf., Busan (Korea), PoS(ICRC2017) 396, also in [arXiv:1708.06592](#).
- [23] A. Blanco et al, "Autonomous RPCs for a Cosmic Ray ground array", Proc. 35th Int. Cosmic Ray Conf., Busan (Korea), PoS(ICRC2017) 379, [arXiv: 1709.09619](#).
- [24]. A. Aab et al. (Pierre Auger Collaboration), "Observation of inclined EeV air showers with the radio detector of the Pierre Auger Observatory", JCAP 10, 026 (2018), [arXiv: 1806.05386](#).
- [25] J. Hörandel for the Pierre Auger Collaboration, "Precision measurements of cosmic rays up to the highest energies with a large radio array at the Pierre Auger Observatory", Proc. of Ultra-High Energy Cosmic Rays 2018, Paris, France (in press 2019).
- [26] R. Smida for the Pierre Auger Collaboration, Proc. 35th Int. Cosmic Ray Conf., Busan (Korea), PoS(ICRC2017) 390, also in [arXiv:1708.06592](#).
- [27] A. Castellina for the Pierre Auger Collaboration, "AugerPrime: the Pierre Auger Observatory Upgrade", Proc. of UHECR2018, Paris, France, (in press, 2019).
- [28] A. Letessier-Selvon et al., "Layered water Cherenkov detector for the study of ultra high energy cosmic rays", Nucl. Instrum. Meth. A767, 41 (2014).
- [29] D. Maurel et al., Proc. of 33rd Int. Cosmic Ray Conf., Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, 600 (2013).

[30] A. Aab et al. (Pierre Auger Collaboration), “Searches for Anisotropies in the Arrival Directions of the Highest Energy Cosmic Rays Detected by the Pierre Auger Observatory”, *Astrophys. J.* 804, 15 (2015), [arXiv: 1411.6111](#).

[31] W. Baumgartner, J. Tueller, C. Markwardt, G. Skinner, S. Barthelmy, et al., “The 70 Month Swift-BAT All-sky Hard X-Ray Survey”, *Astrophys. J. Suppl.* 207, 19 (2013).

[32] M. Niechciol for the Pierre Auger Collaboration, “Diffuse and targeted searches for ultra-high-energy photons using the hybrid detector of the Pierre Auger Observatory”, *Proc. 35th Int. Cosmic Ray Conf.*, Busan (Korea), PoS(ICRC2017) 517 (2017), also in [arXiv:1708.06592](#).

[33] E. Zas for the Pierre Auger Collaboration, “Searches for neutrino fluxes in the EeV regime with the Pierre Auger Observatory”, *Proc. 35th Int. Cosmic Ray Conf.*, PoS(ICRC2017) 972 (2017), also in [arXiv:1708.06592](#).

[34] G. R. Farrar, J. D. Allen, “Testing models of new physics with UHE air shower observations”, *Proc. 33rd Int. Cosmic Ray Conf.*, Rio de Janeiro (Brazil) (2013), [arXiv:1307.7131](#).

[35] R. Aloisio et al., “Are cosmic rays still a valuable probe of Lorentz Invariance Violations in the Auger era?”, *Frascati Phys. Ser.* 58, 274 (2014), [arXiv: 1408.5213](#).
